

Paratuberkuloosiriski suomalaisessa emolehmä-tuotannossa ja eri toimenpiteiden vaikutus siihen

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Abstract

The present report assesses the risk of paratuberculosis spreading into and within Finland. The report further evaluates the impact of various interventions. The aim of the report is to describe the current understanding of the risk of paratuberculosis, and its prevention, in such a manner that information thus gained can be used in the attempt to curb the spread of paratuberculosis both nationally and on individual farms. The evaluation was carried out in accordance with the risk assessment guidelines supplied by the World Organization for Animal Health (OIE).

According to Finnish studies, there have been some cases of paratuberculosis in Finnish beef herds. In 1992, symptomatic paratuberculosis was recorded for the first time in Finland since the beginning of the 20th century. However, it is impossible to reliably evaluate the present prevalence of the disease due to the nature of the available data and, therefore, the risk assessment was carried out qualitatively. Suckler herds were the primary target of the report since they play a key part in the spread of the infection. Data from 2001 was used for the risk assessment.

Over the years, live cattle have been imported into Finland only in small numbers. However, according to available data it appears that the paratuberculosis bacteria was initially introduced to Finland via imported cattle. It was estimated that the risk associated with importing cattle has reduced since 1995; the current risk status was considered to be moderate. The best way to prevent the introduction of paratuberculosis into Finland was considered to be a thorough acquaintance, based on long-term monitoring, of the infection prevalence in the cattle of origin. If tests are not carried out until the animal is in Finland, little protection against possible infection transmission is available due to the long incubation period and problems associated with laboratory testing.

No comprehensive data exists on the prevalence of paratuberculosis in Finnish beef herds. Nevertheless, the significance of various transmission modes was evaluated. Paratuberculosis infection is spread only through contact with an infected animal, faeces or milk. According to the present risk assessment, bought animals pose the most significant risk for a cattle herd to contract paratuberculosis. Buying in cattle from several, often distant, farms is fairly common in Finland. Due

to the long distances involved in cattle movements, no real regional variation are thought to exist but all regions in Finland are either clear of, or uniformly infected with, paratuberculosis. The risk of paratuberculosis spreading from an infective farm to an infection-free farm was considered to be moderate.

There are several methods to curb the spread of infection at a national level. Such methods include the statutory inclusion of paratuberculosis into the list of notifiable diseases, an introduction of a voluntary control programme, the recognition of the disease in the health care of product animals and the allocation of funds towards combating measures against animal diseases. The impact of such measures is related to their application. Since none of these methods are operational at present, it was not possible to evaluate their impact on the risk. According to the report, the most effective ways to prevent the spread of the infection at a national level are to follow the guidelines issued by the Association for Animal Disease Prevention in Finland (ETT), regarding live animal imports, and the sufficient availability of paratuberculosis testing. The use of vaccines against paratuberculosis is considered to have the least impact.

The present report states that the most effective ways to prevent the spread of paratuberculosis into individual cattle herds are: the replacement of live animal acquisition by embryo transfers, abandoning the practice of sharing grazing, water sources, machinery and transport vehicles if any of the participating farms have encountered the infection as well as isolating cattle from any possible infection sources. The next most effective ways were: acquiring new cattle only from farms which are deemed to be infection-free through comprehensive investigations, the replacement of breeding bulls in common use by artificial insemination, exercising particular caution when buying imported animals and using colostrum only from farms where paratuberculosis has not been detected. The inspection of new animals on the farm, and a short-time isolating them from the rest of the herd, offers little protection against paratuberculosis.

If infected animals are identified within a herd, the following measures were considered the most effective to prevent the further spread within the herd: the removal of animals with paratuberculosis from the herd as soon as possible, regular testing of the entire herd as well as the removal of carrier animals and their progeny from the herd. The next most effective ways were considered to be: the weaning of calves, cleanliness of the calf pens, using only colostrum from healthy animals for calves and risk analysis carried out on the farm. According to the report, the removal of infected AI bull's progeny from the herd reduces the risk only slightly.

Conclusions

1. There have been some cases of paratuberculosis in Finnish suckler herds. It is not possible to accurately evaluate the present prevalence due to the nature of the current data.
2. When paratuberculosis has been detected on a farm the best methods to prevent the spread are the monitoring for symptoms, testing all animals and the removal of infected animals from the herd.
3. The interaction between Finnish suckler herds, e.g. animal sales, can be currently considered to pose a moderate risk for the spread of infection between the herds.
4. The infection may spread among the beef herds and also extend to dairy farms.
5. Imported animals may introduce the infection to Finland. The choice of the country and the herd of origin are crucial in reducing this risk.
6. The benefits of statutory or voluntary national measures to combat the disease should be further explored.
7. Further studies are needed regarding the development of diagnostic methods so as to make them faster, more sensitive and economical. Surveillance studies on ruminants and other animals with the potential to spread paratuberculosis are also needed.

Key words	Paratuberculosis, suckler herd, risk assessment
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1. Summary

Paratuberculosis is a chronic intestinal inflammation which mainly affects ruminants. It is caused by the bacterium *Mycobacterium avium* subspecies *paratuberculosis*. Its symptoms include diarrhoea and weight loss, and it will eventually lead to the death of the animal. In 1992, paratuberculosis was recorded for the first time in Finland since the early 1900s. The present report assesses the risk of paratuberculosis spreading into and within Finland. The report further evaluates the impact of various interventions. The aim of the report is to describe the current understanding of the risk of paratuberculosis, and its prevention, in such a manner that information thus gained can be used in decision making regarding the prevention of the spread of paratuberculosis both nationally and on individual farms.

According to laboratory results investigations, there have been some cases of paratuberculosis in Finnish beef herds. However, it is impossible to reliably evaluate the present prevalence of the disease due to the nature of the available data. In 1992–2000, paratuberculosis was detected in five herds in Finland. It was therefore decided to assess the risk only qualitatively and to pay more emphasis on identifying factors influencing the risk and, further, to evaluate the significance of such factors on the spread of the infection. Suckler herds were the primary target of the report since they play a key part in the spread of the infection. The risk assessment was carried out qualitatively because, due to shortcomings in the data, a mathematical, quantitative model would not have given any benefit. The magnitude of risk was described with statements ranging from “non-existent” to “high risk”.

Risk of paratuberculosis spreading into Finland

The risk of paratuberculosis spreading into Finland is mainly dependent on the following: the number of imported cattle, paratuberculosis prevalence in the herd of origin and importing country as well as the monitoring methods of respective countries. So far, the number of imported beef cattle has remained very small, the main import countries being Denmark, Sweden and Germany. Paratuberculosis has been detected in all these countries. In the risk management regarding imported cattle, the infection prevalence in the source cattle is of vital importance. Testing an individual imported animal in Finland will not give a reliable result on the infection status of the animal, due to the long incubation period of the disease and problems associated with laboratory testing. Since 1995, the prevalence of paratuberculosis in the herd of origin has been reasonably well known. Sweden has instigated a paratuberculosis combat programme, which is of moderate benefit when ascertaining the infection status of a particular herd of origin.

According to available data it appears that the paratuberculosis bacteria was initially introduced to Finland via imported cattle. It is difficult to estimate the risk associated with importing cattle but the working group estimated it to have been

high before 1995. The current risk status was considered to be moderate. The risk would increase rapidly if the role of paratuberculosis was no longer considered, to the same degree as it is at present, when decisions are made regarding cattle imports. The import risk would increase rapidly if the number of imported beef cattle was to increase and/or the paratuberculosis status of the herd of origin was to significantly deteriorate from the present situation.

The spread of paratuberculosis into Finland can be curbed by taking the paratuberculosis status of the importing country into consideration in cattle purchases and by acquiring new cattle only from farms which are deemed to be infection-free through testing a sufficient amount of animals repeatedly.

Risk of paratuberculosis spreading within Finland

There have been some cases of paratuberculosis in Finnish suckler herds. However, no comprehensive data exist of the prevalence. It is therefore not possible to assess an individual herd's paratuberculosis risk. Nevertheless, it can be assessed which routes of infection are most significant in spreading the infection. The spread of paratuberculosis infection is only possible when a contact with an infected animal, faeces or milk is present.

According to this risk assessment, bought animals clearly pose the most significant risk for a cattle herd to contract paratuberculosis. Buying in cattle from several, often distant, farms is fairly common in farms with suckler herds. Suckler herd farms also often sell bulls, calves and heifers to many other farms. Furthermore, cows are also bought and sold to some extent, which further increases the risk of acquiring an animal with the potential to spread the infection. Animals are usually sold to other suckler herds, but also to farms with dairy cattle. Paratuberculosis may thus spread from suckler herds to dairy herds. Due to the long distances involved in cattle movements, no real regional variation will be in the paratuberculosis status between different regions, but all regions are either clear of, or uniformly infected with, paratuberculosis.

In addition to bought animals, breeding bulls shared between farms may also spread the infection. According to the survey, a bull was shared in 6–14% of farms between 1985 and 2001. On the other hand, artificial insemination is not considered to spread the infection. Of the interviewed farms, 45% reported having used AI in 2001. Ruminants other than cattle are also capable of spreading the infection to a herd. However, it was considered that they play only a small part in the spread of infection within a herd.

Intermediate factors pose a markedly smaller risk of spreading the infection than live animals. Only 6% of the farms with suckler herds reported sharing grazing with other farms, but according to the survey the use of shared grazing is slightly on the increase. However, sharing machinery and tools which come into contact with animal feed or water was moderately frequent. In 2001, of the interviewed farms 49% shared such machinery or tools with at least one other farm.

Based on the data described above, the working group estimated that the risk of paratuberculosis spreading from a positive farm to an infection-free farm was considered to be moderate.

Preventing the spread of infection within Finland

The present evaluation only looked at measures to prevent the spread of infection as far as the source of infection is concerned. When the practical implementation of individual methods to curb the spread of an individual infection is evaluated the following should be taken into consideration: the impact of the method on disease risk, cost implications and limitations posed by practical problems. The choice of best practice is also dependent on the prevalence of the infection.

There are several methods to prevent the spread of infection at a national level. Such methods include the statutory inclusion of paratuberculosis into the list of notifiable diseases, an introduction of a voluntary combat programme, the recognition of the disease in the health care of product animals and the allocation of funds towards various combating measures against animal diseases. The impact of such measures is related to their application. Since none of these methods are operational at present, it was not possible to evaluate their impact on the risk level. According to the report, the most effective ways to prevent the spread of the infection at a national level are to follow the guidelines issued by the Association for Animal Disease Prevention in Finland (ETT), regarding live animal imports, and the sufficient availability of paratuberculosis testing. The use of vaccines against paratuberculosis is considered to have the least impact.

The present report states that the most effective ways to prevent the spread of paratuberculosis into individual cattle herds are: the replacement of live animal acquisition by embryo transfers, abandoning the practice of sharing grazing, water sources, machinery and transport vehicles if any of the participating farms have encountered the infection as well as isolating cattle from any possible infection sources. The next most effective ways were: acquiring new cattle only from farms which are deemed to be infection-free through comprehensive investigations, the replacement of breeding bulls in common use by artificial insemination, exercising particular caution when buying imported animals and using colostrum only from farms where paratuberculosis has not been isolated. The inspection of new animals on the farm, and their isolation from the rest of the herd for limited time, offers little protection against paratuberculosis.

If infected animals are identified within a herd, the following measures were considered the most effective to prevent the further spread within the herd: the monitoring of animals for symptomatic paratuberculosis and the removal of animals with paratuberculosis from the herd as soon as possible, regular testing of the entire herd as well as the removal of carrier animals and their progeny from the herd. The next most effective ways were considered to be: the weaning of calves, cleanliness of the calf pens, using only colostrum from healthy animals for calves and risk analysis carried out on the farm. According to the report, the removal of infected AI bull's progeny from the herd reduces the risk only slightly.

When the decision is made to take practical measures the following should be considered, in addition to the factors mentioned in the present report: cost implications, the prevalence of the infection and limitations posed by practical problems.

Conclusions

1. There have been some cases of paratuberculosis in Finnish suckler herds. However, it is not possible to accurately evaluate the present prevalence due to the nature of the current data.
2. When paratuberculosis has been detected on a farm the best methods to prevent the spread are the monitoring for symptoms, testing all animals and the removal of infected animals from the herd.
3. The interaction between Finnish suckler herds, e.g. animal sales, can be currently considered to pose a moderate risk for the spread of infection between the herds.
4. The infection may spread among the beef herds and also extend to dairy farms.
5. Imported animals may introduce the infection to Finland. The choice of the country and the herd of origin are crucial in reducing this risk.
6. The benefits of statutory or voluntary national measures to combat the disease should be further explored.
7. Further studies are needed regarding the development of diagnostic methods so as to make them faster, more sensitive and economical. Surveillance studies on ruminants and other animals with the potential to spread paratuberculosis are also needed.